

Determination of heavy metals from *Cressa cretica* using atomic absorption spectroscopic technique

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Abstract : Most of the herbal medicines analysed for heavy metals, are found to be having higher concentration of one or more elements. Therefore, limit tests of heavy metals are essential for herbal medicines. There is also a need for heavy metal analysis to be an integral part of the standardization of herbal medicines. *Cressa cretica* is a common plant growing in sandy regions. It has been used against various ailments of which diabetes, leprosy, anaemia are few to name. Four common heavy metals lead, zinc, copper and nickel were analysed by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). AAS is one of the analytical techniques used for quantitative determination of trace elements.

Keywords : Atomic absorption spectroscopy, heavy metals, *Cressa cretica*.

In the past few years there has been resurgence in the usage of herbal medicine, among the traditional as well as the modern consumers of herbal products. As a result, the demand for high standard, reliable and contaminant free herbal medicine is increasing by the regulatory agencies, consumer groups and manufacturing units.

Heavy metals are a matter of concern in the herbal drugs, especially as certain plants have the tendency of storing heavy metals from the soil, polluted water and atmosphere¹. Out of the various Indian medicinal plants known, *Ocimum sanctum*, *Tinospora cordifolia*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Nerium indicum* and *Acorus calamus* are the few plants which have been analysed for trace elements by Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA). Zinc was found to be higher in *Ocimum sanctum* and *Azadirachta indica* leaves². Although there has been considerable research on the response of plants to heavy metals, the mechanism, which helps plants to survive in metal contaminated environments, is still not very clear. This is particularly evident with respect to the plants having long life span, like trees. Most of the research carried out so far on heavy metals has been on herbaceous or short lived plants³. Studies carried out on higher plants reveal that they can be used as accumulative monitors of many metal elements in polluted areas⁴. There are a number of reports indicating that plants may be able to acclimatize to presence of pollution and contamination³. How-

ever, the complete mechanism of metal tolerance for any plant has yet to be described. There is also limited information available on the limits of metal tolerance and the actual metal concentration above which further adaptation of metal or metals is possible⁵.

Thus, metal tolerance may be the result of genetically inherited physiological mechanism. The ability of a plant to respond phenotypically to a stress may therefore be an important mechanism in the survival of a plant⁶. *Cressa cretica* is a common plant growing in sandy regions. It has been used against various ailments few of which are diabetes, leprosy, anaemia⁷. Four common heavy metals lead, zinc, copper and nickel were analysed by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). AAS is one of the analytical techniques used for quantitative determination of trace elements.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Whole plants of *Cressa cretica* from various geographical regions were collected, powdered and analysed by using AAS. The plant powder was analysed for four heavy metals zinc, copper, nickel and lead.

AAS is the powerful instrumental technique for the quantitative determination of trace metals. The absorption of energy by ground state atoms in the gaseous state forms the basis of AAS.

Results and discussion

The normal range of concentrations of four heavy metals namely zinc, copper, nickel and lead in plants have been presented in Table 1³⁻⁸. The results of this heavy metal analysis using AAS technique have been presented in Table 1. The concentration of copper was minimum ($47.46 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) in Thane, while maximum in Mumbai ($52.63 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). The concentration of zinc was lowest ($27.21 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) in Mumbai and highest at Thane ($30.43 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). In case of nickel, the concentration was minimum ($21.47 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) in Thane and maximum at Mumbai ($29.98 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). The concentration of lead was maximum ($9.53 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) at Thane, while minimum at Mumbai ($6.21 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$).

Amongst the four metals analysed from *Cressa cretica* copper was found to be in maximum concentration and lead in the last concentration in plants of all regions, though they were within the normal range. There were no significant variations in the total metal concentration between various geographical regions, however, individual metal concentration varied in plant powders of different

metals at levels more than normal range reported in other plants. This is specifically true with copper and nickel, however, this seems to be a normal trend with most of the herbal medicines³. The concentration of nickel and copper in *Cressa cretica* is still much lesser than the concentration limit present in plants contaminated with these metals. Since the levels of these heavy metals do not vary with the geographical regions of collection, it may suggest that these higher levels could be related to the normal physiology of the plant. The present study, however, has not determined the levels of these heavy metals in soil for confirming this role of the plant.

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Table 1. Typical concentration (in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) of four metals in plants and in *Cressa cretica* Linn. collected from different regions

Metal	Normal range in plant material fresh weight	Concentration in contaminated plant	Thane	Mumbai
Copper	4-15	20-100	47.46	52.63
Zinc	3-100	100-400	30.43	27.21
Lead	0.1-10	30-300	9.53	6.21
Nickel	0.02-5	10-100	21.47	29.98

regions. Copper and nickel showed significant variation in their range in the analysed metals. These results, however, require further investigation, especially to correlate with the environmental levels of the heavy metals. Thus, *Cressa cretica* as investigated in the present study does not provide ample evidences to indicate pollution related accumulation of heavy metals. Though it is evident from the study that *Cressa cretica* does accumulate some heavy